

A Review on Advancement of Mouth Dissolving Tablets

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ABSTRACT

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Common issues with traditional dosing forms, such as pills and capsules, include dysphagia, which increases the likelihood of noncompliance and renders the treatment ineffective. Mouth dissolving tablets, which have good hardness, dose homogeneity, and ease of administration, have been designed to eliminate the issues with conventional dosage forms. They are the dosage form of choice for pediatric, geriatric, and travel patients. Researchers seeking methods to improve patients' adherence to their prescribed medications have long been interested in developing more complex oral medication delivery systems. By eliminating administration problems and extending the patent life, mouth-dispensing drug delivery systems (MDDDS) have become a dominant player in the industry. There is no requirement for water during administration of MDDDS because they dissolve and release the drug immediately when they meet saliva. Consequently, these dosage forms have attracted a certain demographic of patients, including those with swallowing difficulties, those who are bedridden, those with mental health issues, the elderly, and children. To improve the disintegration quality of these delicate dosage forms without sacrificing their integrity, several new approaches have been developed recently. Considering the unique characteristics of these dosage forms, this paper seeks to give a comprehensive review of the technical progress achieved so far in the evaluation of mouth-dissolving tablets.

Graphical Abstract:

1. Introduction

Orally disintegrating tablets (ODTs), fast-dissolve tablets, and other similar terms describe solid dose forms that dissolve or disintegrate quickly in the mouth without the use of water. This makes dosing much easier, which is great news for those who have trouble swallowing regular pills (1, 2). Mouth dissolving tablets play a crucial role in drug delivery for several reasons:

1. Patient Convenience: They provide an easy-to-swallow dose form, which is especially helpful for patients with swallowing difficulties, including children, the elderly, and people with specific medical conditions (3).

2. Rapid Onset of Action: Medication in mouth-dissolving tablets can be absorbed into the bloodstream more rapidly because of how fast they dissolve or disintegrate in the mouth. (4) This can result in a more rapid start of effect than with conventional oral dosage forms, which is great for treatments like pain relievers and anti-anxiety meds that need to work quickly (5).

3. Improved Compliance: Because they are easy to swallow and have a nice flavour, patients are more likely to follow their prescription regimens, which improves treatment results and decreases the likelihood of missing

doses (6).

4. Accurate Dosage: Mouth dissolving tablets are manufactured to deliver precise doses of medication, ensuring consistent dosing and reducing the risk of dosing errors (7).

5. Enhanced Bioavailability: Some drugs may exhibit improved bioavailability when administered via mouth dissolving tablets due to increased dissolution and absorption in the oral cavity (8).

6. Stability: Mouth dissolving tablets can offer improved stability and shelf life compared to other dosage forms, as they are often less susceptible to degradation from moisture or temperature fluctuations (9).

Overall, mouth dissolving tablets provide a versatile and effective drug delivery option that addresses the needs of patients while offering advantages in terms of convenience, efficacy, and compliance (10).

2. Ideal properties of Mouth Dissolving Tablet

Dissolves or disintegrates in the mouth in a matter of seconds; no water is necessary for swallowing. Work well with flavor masking. Following oral administration, there should be very little to no residue left in the mouth. Show

little to no sensitivity to changes in environmental conditions like humidity and temperature. Permit the inexpensive production of the tablet using standard processing and packaging machinery (11, 12).

3. Techniques of Mouth dissolving Tablet

One possible explanation for how quickly MDTs dissolve is that water dissolves them because it quickly penetrates the tablet matrix. Thus, the fundamental methods for creating MDTs consist of. maximizing the tablet matrix's porosity structure.

- Using the right agent or agents for disintegration.
- Making use of formulation excipients that are very soluble in water (13).

Many approaches have been developed so far, each grounded in a different school of thought. There is a wide range of variation among the produced dosage forms with respect to mechanical strength, drug and dosage form stability, flavour, mouthfeel, rate of dissolution, swallowability, and total bioavailability. A list of various patented technology can be found in Table 1.

Table 1: List of Branded Products Based on patented Technologies

Technologies covered by patents	Technology	Company	Active ingredients
Zydis	Lyophilization	R.P.Schere r,Inc	Loratidine (Claritin Reditab and Dimetapp Quick Dissolve)
Quicksolv	Lyophilization	Janssen pharmaceuticals	Cisapride monohydrate (Propulsid Quicksolv), Risperidone (Risperdal MTab)
Lyoc	Lyophilization	Farmalyoc	Phloroglucinol Hydrate (Spasfon Lyoc)
Flashtab	Direct compression	Ethypharm	Ibuprofen (Nurofen FlashTab)
Orasolv	Direct compression	Cima Labs,Inc.	Paracetamol (Tempra Quicklets), Zolmitriptan (Zolmig Repimelt),
Durasolv	Direct compression	Cima Labs, Inc.	Hyoscyamine Sulfate (NuLev)

			Zolmitriptan (Zolmig ZMT)
Wowtab	Direct compression	Yamanouchi Pharma Tech. Inc.	Famotidine (Gaster D)
Ziplets	Direct compression	Eurand International	Ibuprofen (Cibalgina DueFast)
Advatab	Microcaps and diffuscap CR Technology	Eurand International	AdvaTab cetirizine, AdvaTab Paracetamol
Flashdose	Cotton Candy Process	Fuisz Technology, Ltd.	Tramadol HCl (Relivia Flash dose)
Oraqquick	Micromask taste masking	KV Pharm.Co., Inc	ODD for Hyoscyamine Sulphate

There are several ways to manufacture MDDDS, including:

1. The process of lyophilization
2. Molding
3. Immediate Compression
4. The Cotton Candy Method
5. Utilizing Spray Drying
6. Transfiguration
7. Extrusion in Mass
8. The process of nanonization
9. Easily Removed Films

The process of lyophilization: - The product is sublimated from its water content after the freeze-drying process has frozen it. This method is the foundation upon which MDTs built with the Zydis, Quicksolv, and Lyoc technologies rest. A lyophilized oral formulation was developed by Jaccard and Leyder. It showed improved bioavailability of many drugs, including spironolactone and trolendomycin, and it dissolved quickly (14). Hydrochlorothiazide was used as a model medication by Corveleyn and Remon as they investigated different formulation and manufacturing characteristics (15, 16).

Drugs including loperamide, piroxicam, oxazepam, lorazepam, brompheniramine, olanzepine, ondansetron, and rizatriptan have been formulated using patented processes like Zydis technology (ZT) (17–20). Thirteen products made using this technology are currently available to consumers (21).

Feldene Melt, Zyprexa Zydis, Pepcid RPD, Maxalt-MLT, Dimetapp Quick Dissolve, and Claritin Reditab are the MDT products that are sold in the US. Additionally, loperamide, enalapril, lorazepam, and oxazepam formulations made by Zydis are available worldwide (22).

ZT's unique freeze-drying process distinguishes them significantly from conventional oral delivery systems when it comes to producing finished dose units (23). The following steps are involved in the process:

Step 1:- Is the mass manufacture of an aqueous medication suspension or solution, followed by a precise dosage into blister forms. Since the blister is what gives the tablet its shape, it is an essential part of the entire product packaging.

Step 2: - Involves controlling the final ice crystal size by subjecting the filled blisters to a cryogenic freezing method that was specifically developed for this purpose. The tablets' rapid breakdown is enhanced by ensuring they have a porous matrix. After that, these frozen units are carried to sizable freeze dryers so that the tablets can undergo sublimation, which removes most of the residual moisture.

Step 3: - To ensure stability and protect the product from changing external variables, shut the open blisters using a heat-seal procedure.

Lyoc, a porous and solid galenic form, is created by lyophilizing an oil-in-water emulsion and injecting it right into the blister alveolus (24, 25). Its odd qualities stem from its unique production technique, which involves freezing an emulsion that has thickened (like paste) and contains the active substance either as bulk or as coated microparticles. This material dissolves quickly and can tolerate high doses despite having a low mechanical strength.

The drug-containing matrix is first frozen in an aqueous solution or dispersion, and then the excess alcohol is utilised to remove the water, creating a porous solid called quicksolv [26]. Although the completed product dissolves rapidly, it is only suitable for drugs that have a very little amount of substance and are therefore insoluble in the solvent used for extraction. According to references [27, 28], the ideal pharmacological characteristics for this technique include low aqueous solubility, small particle size (< 50 µm), and strong water stability in suspension.

For both soluble and water-insoluble medicines, the maximal drug loading capacity is 60 mg and 400 mg, respectively (29, 30). The primary problems with

medicinal solutions that dissolve in water include the formation of eutectic mixtures, which lower the freezing point, and the formation of a glassy solid upon freezing, which may collapse upon drying due to the loss of supporting structure during the sublimation process (31, 32, 33).

4. MDTs made via the lyophilization process

Polymers (such as gelatine, alginates, and dextrin) to give the tablets strength and rigidity; polysaccharides (such as mannitol and sorbitol) to give the matrix crystallinity and hardness and to improve palatability; collapse protectants (such as glycine) to prevent the product from shrinking in its packaging during manufacturing or storage; flocculating agents (like xanthan gum and acacia) to provide uniform dispersion of drug particles; preservatives (such as parabens) to inhibit microbial growth; permeation enhancers (such as sodium lauryl sulphate) to improve transmucosal permeability; pH adjusters (such as citric acid etc.) to optimise chemical stability; flavours and sweeteners to improve patient compliance (34–38).

Advantages

Because of its quick melting effect, this method's primary advantage is that it yields tablets with a pleasant mouthfeel and a very short disintegration time.

Disadvantages

Lyophilization is a pretty standard procedure, however it has several drawbacks, such as being costly and time-consuming. Moreover, the resultant product is delicate and not very stable, thus traditional packaging is not appropriate.

5. Moulding of tablets

Water-soluble components are a common ingredient found in moulded tablets, which helps them dissolve quickly and fully. The many tablet molding techniques are listed below.

Procedure for Compression

Creating Bodies Compression moulding involves wetting the powder mixture with a hydroalcoholic solvent before pressing it onto mould plates to produce a wetted mass. Next, a process like that used to create tablet triturates—air drying—is employed to remove the solvent. Although they are less compact than compressed tablets, these tablets' porous nature makes them dissolve faster (39).

The Heat-Moulding Method

The molten mass with the medication distributed is set using the heat-moulding technique (40). A mould, blister packaging, and an agar solution are used to make the tablet in this way. The process begins with a sugar, agar, and drug suspension, which is then transferred to blister packing. After the agar solution has solidified to form a jelly, it is left to cool to room temperature. Finally, the combination is dried under vacuum at a temperature of approximately 30 °C.

Vacuum evaporation molding without lyophilization

The drug excipient mixture (as a slurry or paste) is poured into a mold of the required size using this procedure. After the mixture has hardened into a matrix through freezing, it is vacuum-dried at a temperature somewhere between its collapse and equilibrium freezing points. This leads to the formation of a matrix that is only partially collapsed. Since the former makes use of controlled evaporation from a solid via a liquid phase to a gas, as opposed to sublimation, it differs from the lyophilization process, which uses free unbound solvent. Vacuum drying, as opposed to lyophilization, aids in densifying the matrix and enhancing the product's mechanical strength. To create an MDT with a disintegration period of roughly 20–60 seconds. Pebley et al. (41) made use of a tablet-shaped mould to evaporate a frozen mixture that included a gum (acacia, carageenan, guar, tragacanth, or xanthan), a carbohydrate (dextrose, lactose, maltose, mannitol, or maltodextrin), and a solvent.

Moulding creates solid dispersions, or tablets. The degree to which the drug dissolves in the carrier determines whether a solid solution or dispersion is produced in the matrix (42). It can also be found in the matrix as microscopic particles or even as individual particles.

Advantages

Molded tablets offer better taste and a faster disintegration rate since the dispersion matrix is composed of carbohydrates that dissolve in water. The production of tablets with porous architectures or the usage of components that are physically altered during the molding process improve these qualities. Tablets made using the moulding method are more amenable to industrial scaling than those made using the lyophilization process.

Disadvantage

The molded tablets may erode and shatter when handled because of their low mechanical strength. Hardening can make the pills stronger, but it will lengthen the time it takes for them to dissolve.

6. Direct Compression (DC)

Since tableting excipients with improved flow, compressibility, and disintegration properties are easily accessible, and since conventional tablet production and packaging equipment can be used, this is the simplest and most cost-effective way to manufacture tablets for MDTs. These include sugar-based excipients, effervescent agents, and tablet disintegrants (43, 44).

S. No.	Ideal requirements	Advantages	Limitations
1.	Flowability	Cost effective production	Segregation
2.	Compressibility	Better stability of API	Variation in functionality
3.	Dilution potential	Faster dissolution	Low dilution potential
4.	Rework ability	Less wear and tear of punches	-
5.	Stability	Simple validation	Poor compressibility of API
6.	Controlled particle size	Low microbial contamination	Lubricant sensitivity

a) Disintegrants

The disintegrants utilized in numerous MDT products derived from the DC approach primarily dictate the disintegration rate and, consequently, the dissolving rate. The use of effervescent agents and water-soluble excipients accelerates this process even more. A lot of people have started using this method since superdisintegrants were found (45). Optimizing the disintegrant concentration allows for tablets to disintegrate more quickly. The correlation between disintegrant concentration and disintegration time of tablets turns inverse below a particular concentration. On the other hand, disintegration time either remains relatively constant or significantly drops above the disintegrant's threshold concentration level (46).

In addition to microgranules, Flashtab, another DC-based method, contains drug-coated crystals and disintegrants (47). This method uses two types of disintegrants: a low-swelling-force swelling agent (like starch) and a high-swelling-force disintegrating agent (like modified cellulose) (48). Using a ratio of 8:2 to 9:1, researchers Bi et al. (49) and Watanbe (50) created MDTs from microcrystalline cellulose (MCC) and low substituted hydroxypropyl cellulose (HPC). Because of its ability to absorb water and significantly expand without gelling at

physiological temperatures, Ito and Sugihara explored the possibility of using agar powder as a disintegrant (51).

b) Effervescent Substances

The creation of over-the-counter products frequently employs the proprietary Orasolv technology (OT), which is based on the evolution of CO₂ as a disintegrating mechanism (52–54). There is a subtle fizz to the product, and it contains microparticles. The effervescent component is activated by saliva, which causes the pill to dissolve. The OT was used to create six commercially available medications, including four Triaminic Softchew formulations, Remeron SolTab, and Tempora FirsTabs.

To accomplish quick disintegration, the present method employs the idea of effervescence (55, 56). Here, the medicine is mixed with other excipients (mannitol and magnesium oxide) and then suspended in a suitable polymer (ethyl cellulose, methyl cellulose, acrylate, or methacrylic acid resins) to create the microparticles. The polymeric dispersion is completed by adding magnesium oxide following the addition and mixing of the medication and mannitol. The release promoters in this case are mannitol and magnesium oxide, which help the drug to come out of the polymeric covering. The mixture is delumped and dried at 50 °C for an additional hour following the initial hour of drying. After that, it's dried for one hour at 60°C after passing through an 8-mesh filter. Tablets with a hardness ranging from 1.0 to 2.0 kP are produced by combining and crushing microparticles, effervescent ingredients, and other excipients. The resulting pills are so weak that they break down in the body's fluids in under a minute (57,58). Because the pills are so soft, a specially made packaging system is used to load them into aluminum blisters. A unique technique called particle effervescent couple had been created to lessen their friability. This method coats organic acid crystals with a base substance that is stoichiometrically smaller than the acid. The particle size of the organic acid crystals is deliberately chosen to be greater than that of the base material to guarantee that the acid crystals are evenly coated over the base. In this case, the coating process is initiated by using purified water as the reaction initiator. The organic acid crystals can only undergo further coating before the reaction can proceed. To determine when the reaction must be terminated, CO₂ evolution measurements are utilized. To make tablets, the resulting effervescent pair can be mixed with drug particles coated with polymer and any other required excipients (59).

Despite looking like a typical crushed tablet, Orasolv

tablets are weaker and more brittle than normal tablets because they are only slightly compressed. As a result, a unique handling and packaging technique was created for Orasolv (60). One benefit of a low degree of compaction is that it prevents compression-induced breakage of the particle coating, which is utilized to mask taste.

A second-generation technique called Durasolv was created to create reliable MDTs. Because Durasolv uses a higher compaction pressure during compression than its predecessor, it has a significantly better mechanical strength (61). As a result, production is accelerated and costs are reduced, and it can be packaged in vials or conventional blister packs (62).

Taste-masked coated pellets are inappropriate for adding Durasolv because to its high compaction pressure and low drug loading capacity. Thus, Durasolv technology functions optimally at relatively low quantities of medication (63). The two products that come from using this technique are NuLev and Zomig ZMT. Nevertheless, effervescent excipients' primary drawback is their hygroscopicity, which drives up production costs by necessitating humidity control during processing and product preservation.

c) Sugar-Based Additives

Using sugar-based excipients such xylitol, dextrose, fructose, lactitol, maltitol, maltose, mannitol, sorbitol, starch hydrolysate, polydextrose, and fructose to mask taste and provide for a lovely mouthfeel. One further way DC can make MDTs is by using these excipients, which are sweet and highly soluble in water. Sugar-based excipients have been divided into two categories by Mizumoto et al. (64) according to their rate of dissolution and moldability.

Saccharides of type I, such as lactose and mannitol, have a high rate of dissolution but a low moldability.

Type II saccharides have a low dissolving rate but a high moldability, such as maltose and maltitol. The ability of a substance to dissolve and be squeezed or molded is known as moldability. It does not relate to the process of melting or solvent-wetting to make a real mold. Granulating Type I saccharide with a granulator can increase its moldability.

Saccharide solution type III :-

The approach outlined above serves as the foundation for WOWTAB (65), which uses fluidized bed granulation to treat Type I saccharide's surface with Type II saccharide. This technology has been utilized in the production of

Benadryl Fast Melt tablets. To create a tablet formulation with the ideal hardness and dissolving speed, two types of saccharides are mixed here (66). Thanks to its exceptional hardness, the WOWTAB formulation is more resistant to environmental changes than Zydis or Orasolv. It can be used in blister packaging or regular bottles. It is believed that the WOWTAB's distinctive smooth-melt taste masking technology gives an improved mouthfeel (67).

During the granulation process, high moldable sugar was layered over low moldable sugar to achieve rapid disintegration. The combination was then exposed to a specific humidity treatment. The final tablet's suggested disintegration time was 1–40 seconds, and its hardness was 1.0–2.0 kg (depending on tablet size). The sugar mixture can be combined with different medication classes to create an MDT with the best possible performance characteristics. It was discovered that a suitable proportion of 5–10% w/w of high moldable sugar was adequate to produce the required hardness and disintegration property (68).

To create an MDT, numerous studies combined starch/cellulose with one or more saccharides that are soluble in water (69). Erythritol was determined to be the optimal saccharide due to its fast breakdown, high tolerance, sweetening, and cool mouthfeel caused by its negative heat of solution.

The recently developed Ziplet technology can be used for medications in the form of coated microparticles or pharmaceuticals that are insoluble in water. After adding an appropriate amount of a water-insoluble inorganic excipient and one or more efficient disintegrants, the MDT showed outstanding physical resistance and excellent disintegration, regardless of the compression force or tablet hardness (70). It prevents powder formation or tablet edge fracturing during production and blister pack opening due to its superior mechanical resistance. The most popular water-soluble salts or sugars might also enhance the disintegration qualities more when compared to water-insoluble inorganic excipients. Since most water-soluble component tablets dissolve rather than disintegrate, the disintegration period for these tablets is typically much longer. Reduced water diffusion into the tablet's interior occurs because of the hydrolysis of soluble components on the tablet's surface, creating a concentrated, viscous solution (71).

The Cotton Candy Method :-

An MDDDS manufacturer, FLASHDOSE®, uses a combination of the Shearform™ and Ceform TITM technologies to eliminate the medicine's bitter taste

(72,73). A "floss" matrix made of a combination of excipients, either alone or in combination with drugs, is created using shear form technology. Typically made at temperatures ranging from 180 to 266 °F (74), the floss is a fibrous material that looks like cotton candy fibres and is made of saccharides such as lactose, fructose, dextrose, and sucrose.

Conversely, polymaltodextrins and polydextrose are alternative polysaccharides that can be converted into fibres at temperatures 30–40% lower than sucrose. This modification allows for the secure incorporation of thermolabile pharmaceuticals into the formulation (75). The tablets made utilizing this process are incredibly porous and have a great mouthfeel due to the rapid dissolving of the sugars in saliva. The four steps that make up the manufacturing process are listed below.

I. Blending Floss

This stage involves blending 80% sucrose, 1% surfactant, and mannitol/dextrose to create the floss mix. The surfactant helps to preserve the floss fibers' structural integrity by enhancing crystallization. In addition, it helps an amorphous sugar complex's outer part to become crystalline, which in turn helps the rest of the mass to become completely crystalline. By trapping the disseminated drug within the matrix, this process lessens migration out of the solution (76).

II. Handling Floss

The floss formation machine uses flash flow and flash heat operations to build a matrix from the carrier material. The machinery utilized in the manufacturing of "cotton-candy" is like this one; it also has heating elements and a grinding head. The carrier material experiences an internal flow condition because of the heat induced during the flash heat process. The floss is then drawn in by centrifugal force and sent out through a spinning head that rotates at 2000–3600 rpm. The floss is usually amorphous in structure and is long and thin (77–79).

III. Cutting and Conditioning Floss

The procedure involves the use of a high shear mixer-granulator to reduce the fibres to tiny bits. The floss is conditioned by partially crystallizing it using a 1% ethanol treatment that is sprayed on and then evaporated, giving the floss better cohesive and flow characteristics (80).

IV. Blending and Compression

The last step is to crush the floss fibers that have been cut and conditioned into tablets along with the medicine and any additional excipients that may be required. To further

enhance the mechanical strength of the tablets, a curing process is also carried out, which comprises subjecting the dosage forms to elevated humidity and temperature (40 °C and 85% RH for 15 minutes). The expected outcome is that the floss material will crystallize, bind, and bridge, which will enhance the structural integrity of the dosage form (81).

7. Making Use of Spray Drying

The method that Allen et al. (82) employed to fabricate MDTs was spray-drying. The formulations included mannitol for bulking and sodium starch glycolate/croscarmellose for disintegration, in addition to hydrolyzed and unhydrolyzed gelatine for matrix support. Additional enhancements to disintegration and solubility were achieved by using an acid (such as citric acid) or an alkali (such as sodium bicarbonate). After the excipient suspension was spray-dried, a porous powder was produced that was then compacted into tablets. In an aqueous media, tablets made using this process dissolved in less than 20 seconds.

a) Transfiguration: -

By using sublimation, MDTs with a high porosity might be created. A porous matrix is produced by sublimating compressed tablets containing volatile chemicals and other excipients. Several inert, highly volatile solids have been employed for this function, including ammonium bicarbonate, ammonium carbonate, benzoic acid, camphor, hexamethylene tetramine, naphthalene, phthalic anhydride, urea, and urethane (83). The use of solvents such as benzene and cyclohexane to introduce porosity within the matrix was also considered (Figure 1). The method that was detailed by Makino et al. in 1984 involved the use of water as a material that forms pores.

Figure 1 Development of mouth dissolving tablets

b) Extrusion in Mass :-

This method softens the active blend using a solvent mixture of methanol and water-soluble polythene glycol. A cylindrical extrude is made by forcing the melted mixture out of a syringe or extruder; from this, tablets are formed by cutting the extrude into uniform pieces using a hot blade. This approach can also be used to encapsulate bitter drug granules, making them tasteless (85).

c) The process of nanonization :-

A patented wet-milling approach is used to reduce the drug's particle size to nanosize in a recently developed Nanomelt technology (86). Surface adsorption on certain stabilizers stabilizes the drug's nanocrystals against agglomeration, and these stabilizers are then integrated into MDTs. Medications that aren't easily dissolved in water are ideal candidates for this approach. Another advantage of this technology is the rapid disintegration or dissolution of nanoparticles, which improves absorption, bioavailability, and dosage reduction. Other advantages include a cheap production process, conventional packaging that is remarkably durable, and a wide range of doses (up to 200 mg of drug per unit).

d) Easily Removed Films :-

This is a first for MDDDS, and it provides a very useful method of taking medications and vitamins. Medication and other substances that conceal taste are combined in a non-aqueous solution using this procedure, and Some examples of polymers that can create a film when exposed to water and then evaporated include pullulan, carboxy methylcellulose, hydroxypropyl methylcellulose, hydroxyl ethylcellulose, hydroxyl propylcellulose, sodium alginate, and polyvinyl pyrrolidone. For medications that some people find unpleasant, resin adsorbate or drug-coated microparticles can be added to the film (87). When this film comes into touch with the tongue, it melts or dissolves rapidly, releasing the medication in a solution. Fast drug delivery, disintegration in 5 seconds, flavoring after taste, and paper-thin films smaller than 2 by 2 inches are some of the features of this technology (88).

Advantages of mouth dissolving tablets

- Efficacy in administering to patients with swallowing difficulties, such as the elderly, stroke victims, and those confined to beds; patients with renal failure or other medical conditions who should not swallow; and patients in pediatrics, geriatrics, and mental health who refuse to

swallow (89, 90).

- Adherence to treatment plans for patients who are unable to leave their beds due to disability or for those who are too busy or on the go to have easy access to water.
- The pleasant mouthfeel of MDDDS contributes to a shift in people's fundamental perceptions of pharmaceuticals.
- Compared to liquid formulations, it is easier to administer and dose precisely.
- The advantage of a solid formulation of a liquid medicine.
- A possible increase in the rate of action due to the increased absorption of drugs in the oral cavity, throat, and oesophagus as compared to the stomach (91, 92).
- By decreasing side effects, pregastric absorption can increase bioavailability, lower dose, and clinical performance (93).
- Unveiling fresh avenues for company growth: differentiating products, expanding product lines, managing product life cycles, promoting products exclusively, and extending patent protection (94).

8. Limitations of Mouth Dissolving Tablet

- Limited drug loading capacity :- Yes, mouth dissolving tablets do have a limitation in terms of drug loading capacity compared to other conventional tablet formulations. This limitation arises from several factors:(95 -97).

1. Tablet Size: To ensure quick dissolution in the mouth, most mouth dissolving tablets are on the smaller side. The amount of active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) that can be physically included into the tablet follows this limitation.

2. Formulation Constraints: The formulation of mouth dissolving tablets often requires the use of excipients that promote rapid disintegration and dissolution, such as superdisintegrants and water-soluble polymers. These excipients take up space within the tablet, limiting the amount of drug that can be included.

3. Taste and Sensory Considerations: Mouth dissolving tablets are designed to be pleasant-tasting and comfortable to use, which may necessitate the addition of flavorings, sweeteners, and other taste-masking agents. These additives further reduce the available space for the drug substance.

4. Manufacturing Challenges: Achieving uniform

distribution of the drug throughout the tablet matrix can be challenging, especially at high drug loadings. Uneven distribution can lead to variability in drug release and efficacy.

Convenience and quick action are just two of the many benefits of oral dissolving tablets. However, for medications that require bigger doses, other formulations or dosage forms may be required due to their restricted drug loading capacity.

- Sensitivity to moisture :- Yes, mouth dissolving tablets are generally more sensitive to moisture compared to conventional oral tablets. This sensitivity arises from their composition and design, which often includes water-soluble excipients and rapid disintegration properties.

9. Factors contributing to moisture sensitivity in mouth dissolving tablets

1. Water-Soluble Excipients: Mouth dissolving tablets often contain excipients such as superdisintegrants and water-soluble polymers to facilitate rapid disintegration and dissolution in the mouth. These excipients are inherently prone to moisture uptake, which can compromise the integrity of the tablet (98).

2. Hygroscopic Nature: It is possible that some of the excipients and active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs) utilised in the formulation of mouth-dissolving tablets are hygroscopic, meaning that they absorb moisture from their environment. The tablet's physical qualities, including its firmness, elasticity, or durability, may undergo modifications as a result (99).

3. Storage Conditions: Mouth dissolving tablets should be stored in appropriate conditions to minimize exposure to moisture. Improper storage, such as high humidity environments or inadequate packaging, can accelerate moisture uptake and lead to deterioration of the tablets (100).

4. Stability Concerns: Moisture can degrade the stability of certain drugs, leading to reduced potency or changes in chemical composition. This can impact the effectiveness and safety of the medication (101).

To mitigate moisture sensitivity, manufacturers may use moisture-barrier packaging materials and employ proper storage practices. Additionally, formulation optimization and selection of moisture-resistant excipients can help enhance the stability of mouth dissolving tablets.

- Limited Shelf - life etc:- Yes, the moisture sensitivity of

mouth dissolving tablets can contribute to their limited shelf life. The stability and effectiveness of the medicine over time can be impacted by moisture in several ways, including the breakdown of the active pharmaceutical ingredient (API), changes to the tablet's physical qualities, and the potential growth of microbes (102).

10. Factors contributing to the limited shelf life of mouth dissolving tablets

1. Degradation of Active Ingredients: Moisture can cause chemical degradation of the API, which results in a drop in potency or modifications to the medicinal qualities of the medication.
2. Physical Instability: Moisture uptake can lead to changes in the physical properties of the tablet, such as softening, swelling, or disintegration. These changes can affect the tablet's appearance, texture, and disintegration characteristics.
3. Microbial Growth: Moisture can create conditions conducive to microbial growth, potentially leading to contamination and spoilage of the tablets.
4. Formulation Considerations: The choice of excipients and formulation components can impact the shelf life of mouth dissolving tablets. Formulators must balance the need for rapid disintegration with stability considerations to ensure an acceptable shelf life.

To extend the shelf life of mouth dissolving tablets, manufacturers may employ various strategies, including:

- Selection of moisture-resistant excipients and packaging materials
- Use of desiccants or moisture barrier packaging to minimize moisture ingress
- Proper storage conditions, such as storing tablets in a cool, dry environment away from moisture sources
- Regular stability testing to monitor the quality and integrity of the tablets over time (103-104).

Despite these measures, the inherent moisture sensitivity of mouth dissolving tablets may still result in a shorter shelf life compared to other solid dosage forms. Preserving the efficacy and stability of these dosage forms for their entire shelf life requires meticulous planning of formulation, packaging, and storage conditions.

11. Formulation challenges

Pre - formulation studies:- The physicochemical characteristics and compatibility of the medicinal ingredient with the excipients to be included in the formulation are evaluated in pre-formulation studies. In order to overcome formulation obstacles and provide a stable and effective dose form for mouth-dissolved tablets, multiple pre-formulation studies are necessary (105–106). These studies may include:

1. Solubility Studies: Determination of the drug's solubility in various solvents and pH conditions to identify suitable excipients and optimize formulation parameters for drug dissolution.
2. Compatibility Studies: To ensure that the formulation's excipients are compatible with the drug material and won't interact negatively with it, this evaluation is conducted.
3. Excipient Selection: Excipients are screened and chosen according to how well they work with the drug's active ingredient, how quickly they dissolve, and how well they increase patient acceptance.
4. Hygroscopicity Assessment: Determination of the hygroscopic nature of the drug substance and excipients to understand their susceptibility to moisture uptake and guide formulation development and packaging decisions.
5. Mechanical Properties: Evaluation of the tablet's hardness, friability, and disintegration time, among other mechanical parameters, to guarantee the tablet's correct integrity and disintegration attributes.
6. Taste Masking: Evaluation of taste masking strategies, such as the use of flavoring agents and sweeteners, to enhance patient acceptability of the mouth dissolving tablet.
7. Stability Studies: Conducting stability studies under accelerated and long-term conditions to assess the physical, chemical, and microbiological stability of the formulation over time and identify any degradation pathways or formulation challenges. (107-113)

By conducting these pre-formulation studies, formulators can identify potential formulation challenges early in the development process and design a robust formulation strategy to overcome them. This proactive approach helps ensure the successful development of mouth dissolving tablets with desirable characteristics, including rapid disintegration, stability, and patient acceptability.

Post - formulation studies:- To make sure the finished mouth dissolving tablet is of good quality, stable, and

performs as expected, post-formulation studies are carried out after the formulation process to fix any problems with the formulation. The purpose of these investigations is to evaluate the formed tablets' properties and to find problems that may develop during production, storage, or usage. Some post-formulation studies relevant to addressing formulation challenges in mouth dissolving tablets include:

1. **Dissolution Testing:** Evaluation of the dissolution profile of the formulated tablets to ensure rapid and complete drug release in the oral cavity. Any deviations from the desired dissolution profile may indicate formulation challenges such as inadequate disintegration or dissolution.

2. **Disintegration Testing:** Assessment of the disintegration time of the tablets to ensure they rapidly disintegrate in the mouth as intended. Deviations from the expected disintegration time may indicate formulation challenges such as inadequate use of superdisintegrants or inappropriate compression force during tablet manufacturing.

3. **Mechanical Strength Testing:** Determination of the mechanical properties of the tablets, including hardness, friability, and tensile strength, to assess their physical integrity and resistance to mechanical stress during handling and transportation. Formulation challenges such as insufficient binding agents or improper compression parameters may affect tablet strength.

4. **Stability Testing:** Conducting stability studies to evaluate the physical, chemical, and microbiological stability of the formulated tablets under various storage conditions (e.g., temperature, humidity). Stability testing helps identify any formulation challenges related to degradation, physical changes, or loss of potency over time.

5. **Moisture Uptake Studies:** Assessment of the tablets' susceptibility to moisture uptake and the impact of moisture on their physical and chemical properties. Formulation challenges related to moisture sensitivity may require adjustments in excipient selection, packaging, or storage conditions.

6. **In vitro/In vivo Performance Evaluation:** Evaluation of the bioavailability, beginning of action, and overall therapeutic efficacy of the prepared tablets using in vitro (e.g., dissolving tests) and in vivo (e.g., pharmacokinetic studies) testing. If the tablets don't work as expected, it could be a problem with the formulation.

By conducting comprehensive post-formulation studies,

formulators can identify and address any formulation challenges that may affect the quality, stability, or performance of mouth dissolving tablets, ensuring their effectiveness and patient acceptability.

Techniques to Overcome Limitations (How you will get over the limitation)

Overcoming limitations can be challenging but certainly achievable with the right mindset and strategies. Here are some techniques to help you overcome limitations:

1. **Set Clear Goals :-** Define specific, achievable goals that you want to accomplish despite the limitations. Having a clear target will give you direction and motivation.

2. **Focus on Strengths :-** Identify and leverage your strengths. Concentrate on what you can do well rather than dwelling on what you cannot.

3. **Adapt and Innovate:-** Explore alternative ways of doing things. Be creative and open to new approaches that work around your limitations.

4. **Seek Support :-** Don't hesitate to seek help from others—whether it's family, friends, colleagues, or professionals. Supportive relationships can provide valuable resources and encouragement.

5. **Continuous Learning :-** Invest in acquiring new skills and knowledge. Continuous learning can open up opportunities and empower you to overcome obstacles.

6. **Mindset Shift :-** Think like a student again. Think of difficulties not as obstacles but as chances for development and education.

7. **Time Management :-** Efficiently manage your time and resources. Prioritize tasks and allocate time effectively to maximize productivity.

8. **Stay Persistent :-** Persistence is key to overcoming limitations. Stay committed to your goals even when faced with setbacks.

9. **Celebrate Progress :-** Acknowledge and celebrate small victories along the way. Recognizing your achievements can boost morale and keep you motivated.

10. **Embrace Positivity :-** Maintain a positive attitude. A positive mindset can help you navigate difficulties with resilience and optimism.

Remember, overcoming limitations is often about finding alternative paths and tapping into your inner strengths and external resources. It's a journey that requires patience, perseverance, and a proactive approach.

12. Future Prospects

The prospects of mouth dissolving tablets (MDTs) involve ongoing advancements and considerations in pharmaceutical technology.

1. Enhanced Formulations :- Continued research aims to improve the taste, stability, and effectiveness of MDTs. This includes exploring new excipients, taste-masking techniques, and faster dissolution profiles.
2. Diverse Applications :- MDTs could expand into delivering a broader range of drugs, including biologics and vaccines, thereby enhancing patient compliance and ease of administration.
3. Personalized Medicine :- There's potential to tailor MDTs for specific patient populations, considering factors like age, health conditions, and preferences.
4. Technological Integration :- Integration with digital health tools could enhance medication adherence monitoring and patient education.

13. Conclusion

In conclusion, mouth dissolving tablets have promising prospects in pharmaceuticals, driven by ongoing innovation. However, addressing current limitations such as drug load, manufacturing complexities, and patient acceptance will be key to realizing their full potential in improving medication delivery and patient outcomes.

Conflict of Interest

Author(s) declared no conflict of interest.

Ethical Compliance Standard

NA.

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